

Sustainable materials for electrochemical capacitors

Krzysztof Fic*, Anetta Platek, Justyna Piwek, Elzbieta Frackowiak*

Poznan University of Technology, Institute of Chemistry and Technical Electrochemistry, Berdychowo 4, 60965 Poznan, Poland

Highly tunable properties of materials used for the construction of electrochemical capacitors make them a perfect choice for a broad scope of applications with high power demand. The ability to design the system according to the expected power/energy profile allows them being considered as powerful alternatives to conventional capacitors and batteries. Carbon materials with the developed specific surface area are the most common electrode components of electrochemical capacitors because of their cost, versatile form, availability, easiness of processing, and eco-friendly character. Biomass is frequently used for carbon production, however, among many natural organic materials, only some of them should be regarded as a useful precursor. Ongoing research brings many novel concepts of using bio-derived materials in high-performance electrochemical capacitors. This review article summarizes the progress on the applications of abundant biomaterials and materials derived from biomass in the field. Various 'green' resources have been used as precursors for activated carbons, as binders, or as gel (gelating) agents for solid-state electrolytes. The authors attempt to critically evaluate a commercial potential of these materials upon ongoing trends in research & development of electrochemical capacitors. Pros and cons of utilizing the selected biomass materials are provided and perspectives for their advanced processing are discussed.

Introduction

Continuous growth of high-energy consuming societies across the world and progressing exploitation of fossil fuels stimulate ongoing research in the field of renewable energy sources. Nowadays, most of the national and international agencies have implemented policies toward reduced emission of pollutants and increased contribution of "green" energy in overall. To fulfill these conditions, many types of technologies, using the wind, water flow, solar radiation, and geothermal processes have been introduced. However, their application is not thoroughly established as the use is limited by unpredictable atmospheric conditions. For efficient exploitation of renewable energy characterized by random fluctuations, a combination of various energy storage devices is indispensable. Apart from redox flow

batteries, accumulators, ultimately fuel cells based on hydrogen from electrolysis, application of electrochemical capacitors seems to be a very attractive strategy. They meet strict environmental requirements being reliable and sustainable energy sources, where no pollutant or greenhouse gas is released during the use. Potential applications of electrochemical capacitors also extend for smart grid, stop-start systems in hybrid vehicles, regenerative braking, cranes, etc [1].

Presently, electrochemical capacitors are the subject of great interest of scientific community with aspects of energy storage improvement and management. On the one hand, their highly tunable properties and the possibility to couple with another energy/power storage devices fall well within the scope of desired solutions such as hybrid and/or electric vehicles etc. [2,3]. On the other hand, regarding possible areas of application, a few subtypes of capacitors have been proposed, such as all-solid-state capacitors for wearable electronics [4–6], flexible or stretchable capacitors for roll-up displays and miniaturized electronics

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: Fic, K. (krzysztof.fic@put.poznan.pl), Frackowiak, E. (elzbieta.frackowiak@put.poznan.pl).

[7–11] as well as optically transparent for the smart energy management [12,13]. Various types of capacitor employment involve intensive research devoted to capacitor materials. Many various materials have been studied regarding the performance in specifically applied electrochemical capacitors, as an active electrode material, electrode binder or a component of an electrolyte. Among them, an important place is held by biomaterials and biomass-derived materials because they provide cost-effective, long-term sustainable and biodegradable alternatives for expensive synthetic, often hazardous substrates. Taking into account that the main element of biomass is carbon, heat treatment of natural sources is an excellent and indispensable strategy for preparing carbon which is a common electrode material in electrochemical capacitors. This review handles current reports on the use of abundant materials of natural origin or being products of biomass conversion in electrochemical capacitors. Utilization of bio-derived materials as potential precursors of capacitor components is presented with a critical point of view regarding their real practical application.

Electrochemical capacitors

Energy storage phenomenon in electrochemical capacitors is based on the electrostatic interactions between ions and polarized electrodes, followed by accumulation of these species close to the highly porous carbon material surface [14]. This phenomenon is known as the formation of electric double-layer (EDL), where ions are assembled in the ‘thin’ layer of few nanometers to counterbalance the charge of the oppositely polarized electrode. Schematic presentation of the charged electrochemical capacitor (EC) is shown in Figure 1. Evidently, after soaking the electrode in the electrolyte solution, ions are always present in the pores, independently of the state of the charge; they are not transported from the electrolyte bulk to the electrode/electrolyte interface since the electrostatic interactions are too weak to enforce such a ‘long-distance’ reorganization. NMR studies [15] and molecular modeling [16] suggested that during EDL charging, most likely a quick accumulation/orientation of ions with a simultaneous repulsion of solvent molecules takes place. Furthermore, it is necessary to mention that during

electrode polarization a solvation shell around ions can be distorted and ions might be partially desolvated [17]. This fast energy storage mechanism implies a few features describing ECs. They may be charged and discharged within a very short time providing a high power output [14]. Moreover, a conventional electrostatic accumulation of ions in electrode pores does not have a durability limit; stable performance of these devices reaching a million of cycles has been reported, and this is a great advantage over batteries usually working up to a few thousands of cycles [18,19].

Overall performance of electrochemical capacitor is generally studied by various electrochemical techniques: qualitative cyclic voltammetry, quantitative galvanostatic charge/discharge and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy combining quantitative and qualitative aspects of evaluation. On the one hand, there are many modes and variations of these techniques that depend on the parameter one has to investigate (capacitance, maximum voltage, corrosion, long-term stability) [19]. On the other hand, these three techniques are complementary to each other, and only their comparison gives a comprehensive insight into processes taking place at the interface between the electrode and the electrolyte.

The capacitance of the system is described by the following Eq. (1):

$$C = \frac{I \cdot dt}{dU} = \frac{dQ}{dU} \quad (1)$$

where $I dt$ or dQ represents an elemental charge received upon discharging process within the voltage range dU . To consider capacitors in a practical way, terms of energy E and power P density must be introduced:

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \cdot CU^2 \quad (2)$$

$$P = \frac{E}{t} \quad \text{or} \quad P = \frac{U^2}{4 \cdot ESR} \quad (3)$$

where C stands for the capacitance of the device, U stands for a cell voltage, t represents discharge time, and ESR is an equivalent series resistance reflecting all resistive contributions in the system. To realize opportunities being brought to the development of ECs, one needs to have a look at power vs. energy diagram for different devices (Figure 2). Apparently, ECs serve as a compromise between physical capacitors (high power but very low energy density) and batteries (moderate power but high energy density); they perfectly fill the gap between both types of storage devices. Moreover, the ability to adjust the power/energy profile of a capacitor to the particular case let them be considered as a versatile choice whenever a reliable power source is needed. Recently, a huge effort is being made to increase energetic output. However, one must notice that the principle of electrochemical capacitors is always to deliver the charge in a very short time [21].

However, comparison of capacitor performance presented in the literature is very often not objective, quite often the authors did not mention the conditions of measurements. This practice usually leads to the wrong estimation of the capacitor metrics. Especially, the results made in a three-electrode system do not reflect the real capacitor behavior; sometimes the values are measured only at a very gentle charge/discharge regime and with a limited mass of ca. 1 mg. In this specific case, the capacitance values and specific power/energy are usually more attractive than

FIGURE 1

Schematic representation of charged electrochemical capacitor [20].

FIGURE 2

Energy vs. power plot for different power sources.

for higher mass loadings, since the impacts of electrode wettability and mass transport are negligible. It has been proven in many reports that the scale-effect is non-linear and shifting toward significantly higher mass loading leads to serious overestimation. Furthermore – quite often the authors do not indicate if they measure electrode potential or voltage of the system. The Ragone plots are frequently shown to compare various capacitor materials. Unfortunately, the values calculated from three-electrode tests, being sometimes presented, absolutely have no sense and meaning. Three-electrode tests and capacitance values obtained from these experiments cannot give reliable results but they are still useful for initial screening of the material properties. The specific energy/power calculation should be strictly limited to the experiment with two-electrode cell. Since all electrochemical devices are always composed of two electrodes and charge must flow from one electrode to another one, the energy/power can be delivered by the system only, not by one electrode, as one cannot make applause with one hand. Finally, it has to be stated that one should calculate the energy/power of capacitor system using constant power discharge as the most trustworthy method. Moreover, it is necessary to underline that energy/power values estimated for electrode materials will be at least 4 but in practice even more times higher than for real capacitor device [22]. Additionally, two-electrode laboratory system can be realized in various constructions (Swagelok, button, pouch cell) but the resistivity of these systems will vary a lot and might be seriously affected by the skills of the researcher. Generally, construction of the system, i.e., a tight contact of electrodes with the current collector, excellent adhesion, the wettability of electrode by the electrolyte, constant internal pressure, has more influence on performance and charge propagation than electrode material itself.

General concepts of electrochemical capacitors

Growing interest in the technology of electrochemical capacitors has brought up many concepts for realizing a suitable and high-performance device. It has to be underlined that most of the electrochemical capacitors are based on carbon materials, namely activated carbons, because of price, disposal, the possibility of modification, etc. Researchers have proposed many carbonaceous materials with a variety of functional [23] and textural properties [24]. Depending on the porous structure, size and shape of pores, amount of the charge stored, and its propagation during charging/discharging differ significantly. Functional groups (containing oxygen, nitrogen, boron, sulfur, phosphorus) present on the carbon surface may induce another interesting effect – pseudocapacitance [17,21,25,26]. While a typical charge storage mechanism in electrochemical capacitors is based on electrostatic interactions, pseudocapacitance originates from redox reactions taking place at the electrode/electrolyte interface [20]. This coupling of typical EDL charging and electron-mediated reaction results in higher current output, and higher overall capacitance [21].

As stability during an on-duty performance is a major issue of concern, to form long-term durable electrodes, carbon materials are usually bound with various polymers. Nowadays, poly(tetrafluoroethylene) (PTFE) and poly(vinylidene difluoride) (PVDF) are widely used, both in academia and industry. They provide high mechanical strength and flexibility (PTFE), however, they aggravate electrode wettability toward electrolytes. The high content of fluorine in mentioned polymers suggests a negative impact on the environment [27] and problematic process of degradation, including ionizing radiation [28].

Regarding electrolytes, one may distinguish three main groups: aqueous, organic, and ionic liquids and apply them

FIGURE 3

Interdependence of electrolyte properties and electrochemical capacitor features.

accordingly to the specific needs. As shown in Figure 3, electrolyte plays a crucial role in EC performance affecting accessibility to pores depending on the ion size; matching of solvated ions with pore size plays a key role [24,29]. Type of electrolyte decides on the operating voltage window as well as the effective temperature range of capacitor. Conductivity and concentration of electrolyte determine capacitance as well as the time constant of the device whereas electrochemical stability is requisite for long-term cycling.

Organic electrolytes, composed of an ionic substance dissolved in the organic solvent, have been established in the industry as the most versatile. They provide high energy output due to wide operational voltage. However, low conductivity, eco-hazardous character, and manufacturing involving air- and moisture-free atmosphere provoke the development of alternatives. On the other hand, aqueous electrolytes are considered as an environmentally friendly approach creating a high-power and cost-efficient device. Assembling does not require demanding conditions, such as handling in the inert atmosphere and expensive extra-drying of all utilized materials; and high values of conductivity ensure excellent price/capacitance ratio. The major drawback of water-based electrolytic solutions is a narrow

range of operational voltage (thermodynamically ~ 1.23 V). However, recent studies have reported that one might overcome that feature by using for example neutral (in terms of pH) or redox-active electrolytes [30–33]. Recently another interesting approach has been proposed utilizing significant pH gradient between two electrodes by their ammonia treatment [34].

Ionic liquids (ILs) have been proposed as a solution that may bring many opportunities of two aforementioned types of electrolytes and couple their beneficial properties. On the one hand, these molten salts provide wide operational voltage window but a moderate value of conductivity and relatively high value of viscosity which affect the ions movement in the bulk of electrolyte [35]. Combined with some type of electrode materials, e.g., silicon nanostructures [36,37] they reveal good electrochemical performance. The use of ILs is also a starting point for the preparation of solid-state electrolytes with suitable polymers [38]. On the other hand, one should be aware that the detailed description of the environmental impact of ILs is still being missed. Concerning them as “green solvents”, due to their remarkably low volatility in comparison to traditional organic solvents, placed ILs on the top of the eco-friendly electrolyte ranking; however, their exact decomposition mechanism (due to thermal/electrochemical degradation) is still unknown. It cannot be neglected that in the production line many organic solvents are used but these issues are very often oversight and covered with an *eco-friendly* label. Air/moisture free conditions of manufacturing and high price limit the broad application of ILs.

Electrode materials

Electrode material and electrolyte are the key components of electrochemical capacitor [39]. The role of efficient charging of electrode/electrolyte interface by ions is essential [20]. Thus, this is quite evident that the higher the accessible surface area, the higher the capacitance. Definitely, that trend is limited by the electronic properties of the electrode material – development of the specific surface area usually makes thinner the pore walls and screening effects start to affect the capacitive properties remarkably. The specific surface area of the porous materials is investigated by the nitrogen adsorption (at 77 K) and then calculated from BET equation [40] but one should not identify these values with electrochemically accessible surface. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that for both recently used models, i.e., based on BET and NL-DFT equations [41,42], there are limits in the capacitance vs. specific surface area dependence. It appears, that the pore volume (essentially in the range of micropores) correlates much better with the specific capacitance than the specific surface area [17,20]. For that reason, the electrode pore size distribution cannot be neglected because ions’ pore size matching is a very critical issue [14]. It is noteworthy to underline that not only size of pores determines capacitance values. Intrinsic capacitance of carbon can vary from 5 to 50 $\mu\text{F}/\text{cm}^2$ depending on carbon structure, i.e., basal, edge sites as well as its electronic properties. Apparently, it seems that the limits of purely capacitive properties of the activated carbons have already been reached [43]. Recently, the development of the carbon-based materials is oriented toward obtaining suitable pore size (vs. electrolyte applied) with efficient pore intraconnection for

enhanced charge propagation and chemical stability during long-term cycling. Among a variety of electrode materials that have been proposed, i.e., graphene [44,45], carbon nanotubes [46], carbide-derived carbons [7,47], carbon onions [48], templated carbon nanostructures [49], carbon microspheres [50] and nanoporous zeolite-derived carbons [51–53] as well as their composites with conducting polymers [54], undoubtedly, activated carbons (AC) have attracted significant attention as a high electrochemically available surface area, cost-efficient and versatile material. One should be aware, that to date, commercially

available activated carbons are usually obtained from well-abundant, natural precursors. Although the templated carbons are characterized by promising electrochemical properties and are extremely useful in fundamental research, their large-scale synthesis is rather doubtful. Development and further efforts in carbonization procedures seem to be necessary for considering them as industrially scalable.

A general overview of various electrode materials and electrolytes with different values of capacitance and operating capacitor voltage is presented in Figure 4. It is worth mentioning that

FIGURE 4

Comparison of capacitance and operating voltage for various electrode materials and electrolytes.

nanocarbons such as nanotubes, graphenes, and nanofibers in the pure form are strictly mesoporous material and can provide moderate values of capacitance 20–60 F/g. However, after activation or functionalization of nanocarbons, these values are significantly higher. Activation of graphene can significantly increase the specific surface area over 2000 m²/g with capacitance values of 200 F/g in an organic medium, but one could not imagine its practical application in short-term perspective [55]. The main obstacle for the moment is a problematic scale-up of high-quality graphene production and low volumetric capacitance, originating from low density of this material. Of course, densifying the material must be considered for the real device assembly, but the electrode processing usually aggravates their ‘extraordinary’ properties. On the other hand, such nanomaterials are the perfect support for pseudocapacitive materials (oxides, electrically conducting polymers, ...). Activated carbons could provide the specific capacitance on the level of 300 F/g, however, it needs to be stated that such high values have been reported most often for proton-rich medium like sulfuric acid and for materials with high oxygen content. In this case, high capacitance values originate from pseudocapacitive effects provided by redox-active oxygen-based functionalities, like quinone/hydroquinone couple. Both abovementioned features could be considered as the disadvantages of such systems. Very low pH of electrolyte enforces selection of current collector, which has to be made of noble and corrosion-resistant metals. Moreover, oxygen incorporated in carbon surface functionalities results in higher resistivity of the system leading to decrease in the power performance, higher self-discharge (due to redox shuttling effects), and poor cyclability. Asymmetric configurations mentioned in Figure 4 (where generally activated carbon as positive electrode is combined with different type of negative electrode) have a wide range of operating voltage from 2 to 4 V in the organic electrolytic medium. This strategy is being developed rapidly with great success in both aprotic and aqueous media [56]. An important issue concerning high-voltage systems is the stability of the electrolyte and the remarkable influence of the electrode porosity on the final operating voltage. Recently, ionic liquids are claimed to operate at 3.0 V or even more on glassy carbon electrodes [57]. Their stability at planar electrodes is ‘impressive’ and for specific applications (like electrodeposition of metals) is absolutely favorable but for energy storage systems like electrochemical capacitors, with porous, activated carbon-based electrodes that value is suppressed due to presence of small and narrow pores, not adjusted to the ions’ size [58]. Once more, the value of voltage recorded for both electrodes individually cannot be directly transferred to the behavior of 2-electrode system, since the final voltage (and electrolyte stability) is governed by two electrodes. Furthermore, porous materials introduce non-homogenous current distribution throughout the electrode and then, the local increase in current density (especially at the defects) provokes electrolyte decomposition.

Considering asymmetric systems, one should critically notice that even if the capacitance values of transition metal oxides and some conducting polymers, e.g., polyaniline as electrode material can demonstrate enormous values exceeding 1000 F/g in the three-electrode cell, the real two-electrode capacitor will supply definitively lower values around 200 F/g per electrode. The

calculation of capacitance in the case of different charge storage is clearly presented in the paper [59]. The capacitance measured in a narrow potential range using three-electrode configuration does not reflect either effective or meaningful capacitance values. Additionally, careful testing of the electrode materials according to international standards (galvanostatic discharging at the regime of 1 A/g, floating experiments, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy) should always be applied by scientists to verify some ‘extraordinary’, ‘outstanding’ and ‘impressive’ results. In this place it is worth to remind that cyclic voltammetry is not an appropriate technique for verification of the cyclic stability; although this kinetic method indicates the qualitative performance perfectly. For the cyclic stability one should consider constant current/voltage techniques only. Moreover, for practical application rather volumetric capacitance as well as volumetric energy and power are more important than gravimetric values because the space for power device is often limited.

Activated carbons

Presently activated carbon (AC) is a key electrode material of electrochemical capacitors being widely used in commercial devices. ACs can be obtained using synthetic or natural precursors rich in carbon [60–62]. The preparation process is based on the carbonization step – high-temperature treatment under inert gas atmosphere, and usually followed by the activation using chemical (KOH, H₃PO₄, ZnCl₂) [63] or physical (CO₂, steam) [64] activating agents. Among various activators, it should be mentioned that some processes, e.g., KOH activation are hardly introduced industrially, or even if it is used, the final activated carbon is definitively more expensive. Typically, industrial activated carbon of high quality for capacitor usage is obtained by steam or carbon dioxide activation (Norit, Kuraray). As the binder-free carbon electrodes, the carbon cloth, e.g., Kynol is inevitable. It is prepared from phenolic resins in one-step synthesis with activation process at the same time.

Activated carbons made of biomass are of particular interest due to the fact, that synthesis involves renewable, common resources. Apart from that, they have unusual properties originating from the relatively high content of different elements providing: (i) pseudocapacitive contribution, (ii) higher electron density, (iii) simultaneous activation.

Recently an interest in using biomass as a precursor for activated carbon is enormously growing. As a rule of thumb, whatever plant after heating at high temperature and inert atmosphere will give a char which by activation process can be transformed into activated carbon. The authors quite often select biomass without considering a carbonization yield, elemental composition, availability, price, etc. These issues are reasonably raised and discussed in a comprehensive review on nanostructured activated carbons from natural precursors provided by Yushin et al. [65]. Typically, carbonization yield of biomass is in the wide range from 30–50% strongly depending on the type of precursor and preliminary drying. Especially, the price of precursor and carbon material is scarcely mentioned in the literature. Cost of the raw natural precursor is generally low <4 USD/kg [57], however, a price of good carbons for capacitor application is quite high because of the activation process and special

FIGURE 5

Biomass-derived activated carbon precursors.

purification. It is also the general rule that the most available precursor material, the lower cost of final carbon.

Different carbon precursors (shells, seeds, grains, seaweeds, leaves with stems) have been studied (Figure 5). For example, the carbonization of various flowers is highly doubtful [66] and without sense because of scarce availability but also carbonization yield, i.e., carbon content in the product is extremely low. Nevertheless, edible products have to be definitively avoided apart from leftovers, especially considering the present world situation, where people habituated in many regions suffer from hunger. Unfortunately, extremely high number of papers appear on carbonization of many nutritious products, e.g., cabbage leaves [67], eggs [68], proteins, etc. Not accidentally coconut shell – well-abundant material, and characterized by the compact structure is one of the most popular biomass precursors of activated carbon [69].

SEM image examples of widely used activated carbons are shown in Figure 6. Significant differences in their morphology are observed for fibrous Kynol material and Black Pearls 2000 whereas Norit and Kuraray samples look quite comparably. The price of such materials ranges from 30 to 50 USD/kg (laboratory scale). Carbon with a more developed specific surface area of $2090 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, a total pore volume of $1.05 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$ and better conductivity, i.e., YP-80F costs more than activated carbon YP-50F characterized by $1700 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and $0.72 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$. Typical nitrogen sorption isotherms at 77 K and pore size distribution for presented carbons are revealed in Figure 7.

The capacitance of biomass-derived carbons found in the literature reaches a wide range of values from moderate 50 F/g to enormously high over 350 F/g. However, the measurements are performed at different and incomparable conditions (galvanostatic regime from 20 mA/g to 50 A/g, voltammetry at a low scan rate of 2 mV/s until 5 V/s). Additionally, the results obtained in three-electrode cell with an excess of electrolyte do not reflect real conditions in two-electrode capacitor device where compact construction with a minimal amount of electrolyte is ensured.

On the other hand, the authors often present capacitance results where the mass load of the electrode is around 1 mg per 1 cm^2 or less. Yet, industrial electrochemical capacitors have loading in the range 5–10 mg/cm² depending on expected capacitor power rate. This again raises the issue of transformation of the results from mg to kg scale. Ruoff et al. indicated general errors made during experiments and capacitance estimation [70]. From practical point of view, specific volumetric capacitance is definitively more important than gravimetric capacitance [71]. On the other hand, miniaturized capacitors for electronics could have obviously extremely low active mass loading.

Among bio-derived activated carbons of high heteroatom content, those rich with nitrogen have been extensively studied in a range of applications, including energy storage devices [72]. The presence of nitrogen-containing groups has a dual function. First of all, a lone electron pair present on the molecular orbital of nitrogen atom increases the electron density across the

FIGURE 6

SEM micrographs of different ACs: (a) Norit Super 30; (b) Kuraray YP80F; (c) BP2000; (d) Kynol 507–20.

material structure that enhances charge propagation significantly and produces electron donor regions. Secondly, it is assumed that in-plane pyridinic groups might introduce the defects in the graphene layers (one pyridine group = two vacancies on carbon) and thus increase the interfacial, edge-site capacitance. N-rich activated carbons can contribute to faradaic reactions, due to highly reversible protonation of nitrogen. The type of N incorporation into carbon matrix and the final N content in the electrode material have also an important impact on the final performance. Usually, pyridinic and pyrrole-like functionalities contribute to the pseudocapacitive charge storage because of their electron donor character. Nitrogen atoms in imides and lactams have been proposed to be electroactive due to their edge locations and the conjugation within their six-membered rings [73,74]. The acidic/alkaline character of nitrogen may differ depending on the product, but pseudocapacitive properties are usually revealed at low pH values of the electrolyte. It has been proved that the capacitance values measured in the neutral and organic medium are definitively lower because of the lack of protons. For this reason, in order to achieve extraordinary high capacitance values, investigations have usually been conducted with sulfuric acid as electrolyte. However, it has been proven that such materials are capable of accumulating and delivering charge with a very high efficiency [75] in Li_2SO_4 electrolyte. Thus, combining highly capacitive material with high-voltage electrolyte can result in the satisfactory energy density

output. Possible reaction with proton participation is shown in Figure 8.

Researchers have already reported many precursors for nitrogen-rich carbon materials from renewable resources, including biopolymers and food wastes [77]. Rufford et al. proposed coffee grounds carbonization to obtain highly microporous material activated with ZnCl_2 [78]. Its performance has been studied in 1 M H_2SO_4 and appeared to be very promising by reaching over 350 F/g of specific capacitance (per mass of one electrode). Another food industry by-product, collagen, has been reported by Ying-Hui Lee et al. [79]. Collagen, as one of the most abundant protein, was cross-linked with paraformaldehyde, followed by carbonization process. Preparation procedure does not involve activation, thus from a practical point of view may be of keen interest. Electrochemical studies have been performed in acidic medium and shown excellent charge propagation at a range of sweep rate values. Additionally, one may notice broad peaks of nitrogen protonation origin. Similar research has also been performed on the other proteins, such as egg white [68]. On the other hand, gelatine-derived carbon has been employed as an active material of the capacitor operating in alkaline electrolytic solution. Herein, the pseudocapacitive effect may also be observed, but its mechanism has a different origin [80]. Nitrogen-rich silk fibroins have been proposed as an attractive precursor for activated carbon providing high energy in organic electrolytes [81]. Regarding natural biopolymers, glucosamine

FIGURE 7

Comparison of various bio-derived AC: (a) nitrogen sorption/desorption isotherms at 77 K; (b) micro- and mesopore volumes.

FIGURE 8

Proposed mechanism of nitrogen contribution to pseudocapacitance [76].

has been shown to be likewise an interesting precursor [82]. Ordered polymer substrate structure results in a uniform product, remarkably affected by the activation conditions using KOH, and

tested out in acidic and alkaline electrolytes. Nonetheless, activation with potassium hydroxide leads to a substantial removal of nitrogen-containing function groups what afterward influences

the electrochemical performance of the material. Cyclic voltammograms show broad reversible peaks with current values dependent on the amount of KOH involved in the process of activation (Figure 9). It is necessary to underline that KOH activation gives developed specific surface area but it is quite an aggressive process and requires special laboratory equipment. Industrial realization of the KOH (or alkali at all) activation is very rare and increases the price of the final material remarkably, mainly because of the equipment degradation and complicated washing procedures. The electrochemical results were obtained only in the three-electrode cell; at the soft regime (1 mV/s) relatively high capacitance values of 250 F/g have been obtained (Figure 9) but charge propagation would be rather moderate with higher current loads. It seems that maximal specific energy values (per mass of both electrodes) should be 8.7 Wh/kg, not 55 Wh/kg. Higher energy values could be reached only at operating voltage close to 2.5 V.

On the other hand, a seaweed biopolymer – sodium alginate has been reported as an excellent substrate for no-activation production of N- and O-rich activated carbon, providing an excellent electrochemical performance in acidic medium [83]. The optimal carbonization temperature for this self-activated biomaterial was 600 °C, whereas the total yield after carbonization and acid leaching was 16%. As far as all of the substrates are considered, the yield value seems to be relatively high. It is important to specify whether the yield is calculated taking into account the carbon material before and after process only or the mass of activator is also considered – detailed calculation dramatically influences the final result. Interestingly the value of capacitance in acidic medium for this carbon was comparable to Maxsorb (190 F/g). However, the specific capacitance per surface unit was 73 $\mu\text{F}/\text{cm}^2$ (for Maxsorb only 6 $\mu\text{F}/\text{cm}^2$). Hence, the volumetric capacitance was more than twice higher as well. Similarly, a mixture of glucose and microalgae has been studied as a source of N-doped carbon and tested out in the neutral electrolyte of LiCl [84,85]. The assembled capacitor has shown promising performance in a narrow operational voltage reaching

over 150 F/g per electrode mass. Though, no signature for faradaic contribution has been observed.

Moreover, many more natural precursors for N-rich activated carbons have been reported, but in a rather fundamental way, not always including the application to electrochemical capacitors [86,87]. They all seem to be very attractive and relatively cheap precursors for activated carbon materials. Certainly, their local abundance is worth considering. Nevertheless, N-rich bio-carbons may be regarded as a real alternative for the future due to low cost and enhanced conductivity [88]. However, the maximal beneficial nitrogen content cannot exceed 8 wt.% [76]. Nitrogen content itself is important [89,90] but the kind of functionalities plays the crucial role [23,91]. As mentioned earlier, pyridinic and pyrrolic nitrogen display pseudocapacitance contribution, while quaternary and pyridinic-N-oxides are beneficial at high current regimes due to relatively high electronic conductivity of the materials enriched by such functionalities. The most revealing fact states that there is a correlation between the normalized capacitance and amount of nitrogen-containing functional groups. It clearly proves the importance of surface chemistry studies.

Some activated carbon materials have also been synthesized from biomass [92–95], but electrochemical studies have not revealed any information about the content of functionalities. Particular attention has been paid to carbons derived from tobacco stems [96], simultaneously activated during carbonization process (600–800 °C) and showing high values of capacitance (240 F/g) in the aqueous electrolyte (1M Li_2SO_4) and in the organic medium (1 M TEABF₄ – 140 F/g). The presence of alkali metals well-distributed in the precursor at the atomic scale was at the origin of self-activation and final carbons with narrow pore size distribution and high specific surface area exceeding 1700 m²/g. In this case, elimination of activation process gives a great profit in total carbon manufacturing. A similar attempt has been made by Xiaojun He et al., who proposed carbonization of a peanut shell and rice husk to obtain activated carbon studied in 6 M KOH and organic electrolyte [97] and also in 1 M H_2SO_4 [98]. Researchers have also shown that banana fibers [99] or coniferous pine [100] may be used as a precursor as well. However, values of capacitance were not outstanding. Application of surfactants allowed researchers to produce a few more bio-derived carbons from lignin, pectin, alginates, agarose, sucrose and some of them have shown a slight contribution coming from the presence of nitrogen-containing functionalities [101–106].

However, it has to be noted that acidic medium should be rather excluded as the electrolyte for practical application owing to the need of the noble current collectors. Majority of commercially available ECs operates in organic media with Al collectors where pseudocapacitive phenomena do not contribute.

Other carbon-based materials derived from biomass

Pressing demand for production various types of carbon materials from renewable biomass resources oriented many investigations toward this field of study.

It has been recently proved that beside typical methods of carbon nanotubes production (e.g. laser ablation [107], arc discharge [108], chemical vapor deposition (CVD) [109]), many

FIGURE 9

Performance of glucosamine-derived activated carbon in the three-electrode system at the scan rate of 1 mV/s in 6 M KOH [82].

research groups are nowadays focused on a sustainable technology. For example, it has been presented that camphor [110], eucalyptus oil [111], waste cooking palm oil [112] and neem oil [113] have been presented as starting materials for CNT production. In addition, rice straw as abundant lignocellulosic waste (production at the level of 650–975 million tons/year [114,115]), has been proposed as the potential biomass for CNT preparation. N.A. Fathy [116] has developed the method for the production of CNTs using CVD of camphor through carbonization of hydrothermally treated rice straw supported with ferrocene or ferrocene-nickel catalyst which allowed obtaining different structures of CNTs with outer diameter ranging from 22–66 nm. Another group presented CNTs with outer diameter 10–20 nm made of wood fibers via continuous oxidation at 240 °C and cyclic oxidation at 400 °C [117]. Bamboo charcoal was also utilized as precursor to produce CNTs via CVD in the presence of ethanol vapor and temperature between 1200 and 1400 °C [118]. Another growing environmental concern was focused on carbon fiber (CF) manufacturing. It has been shown for many times that polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-based CFs [119] have already been replaced by the low-cost precursors. For instance, activated carbon fibers (ACFs) were produced from silkworm cocoon waste via the combination of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ -pretreatment and KOH activation [120]. It has been also demonstrated that ACFs could be also prepared from various biomass resources, i.e., flax fiber [121], oil palm fiber [122] and cotton fiber [123]. Low-cost carbon fiber could be also made of lignin as the renewable precursor [124].

There is also a possibility of obtaining sustainable nanoporous carbon spheres using HTC synthesis [125]. For instance, plant

materials, i.e., cellulose could be used as bio-mass derivatives for abovementioned method. It is characterized by simplicity and consists of 4 steps: dehydration, condensation, polymerization, and aromatization. However, the process does not allow the controlling of the porosity and morphology in the final sample. This challenging issue is still waiting for being solved.

Binders

Carbon electrodes are usually bound with fluoropolymers, such as PTFE and PVdF. The function of a binder is to keep the electrode material integrity during the long-term performance. Hence, the research focused on binding substances is very crucial. In the case of fluorine-containing polymers, the affinity of the electrode to be wetted is moderate. What is more important, fluoropolymers are non-biodegradable, and degradation procedure involves complicated/expensive processes. To follow the idea of sustainable technology, a few bio-binders have been proposed lately. Cellulose, the most common abundant biopolymer, has been reported (Figure 10) as a binder in composition with poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) or on its own [126]. The authors present an interesting idea of the electrode preparation with the recovery step of EMIM acetate (method A in Figure 10). Cellulose-based electrodes display thermal stabilities comparable to those with conventional PVdF binder.

Electrochemical studies have shown a good performance in aqueous (1M Na_2SO_4 at 0.8 V), organic (1M Et_4NBF_4 in PC at 2.5 V) and ionic liquid electrolytes (PC/PYR₁₄TFSI 1:1 wt. at 3.5 V) and no difference between pristine and PEO-doped cellulose. Typically, ESR values were the highest for ionic liquid (10 ohm/cm^2), then for organic electrolyte (6 ohm/cm^2) and the

FIGURE 10

Two pathways to obtain cellulose-bound carbon electrodes [126].

lowest (2 ohm/cm²) for aqueous sulfate solution that results from their different conductivity. Efficiency and capacitance retention vs. 20 000 cycles have been well preserved for all three types of electrolytes. Hence, a natural, abundant, and cheap material such as cellulose can be successfully used as a binder in the eco-friendly EDLCs manufacturing (replacing not sustainable fluoropolymers).

The more specific investigation has been performed with carboxymethylcellulose (CMC) [127,128]. Its solubility in water limits the application only to organic electrolytes, and results proved CMC to be a green alternative for conventional binders. Recently, chitin as another abundant biopolymer has been reported as a binder for activated carbon electrodes [129]. Chitin-bound electrodes have been studied in neutral aqueous electrolytes of Li₂SO₄ (redox-inactive) and KI (redox active) solutions and shown promising performance (comparable to PTFE-bound ones) with an additional benefit coming from trapping of electrogenerated iodine. A slightly different approach has been made using chitosan (CS), a product of chitin deacetylation [130]. Namely, chitosan was cross-linked with glutaraldehyde to form a stable binder. Its performance has been studied in CS-based gel electrolyte soaked with Na₂SO₄ and supported by theoretical study.

The same research group has successfully used casein from bovine milk as a binder [131]. Adhesion strength of electrode to current collector was better (1187 kPa) than in the case with PVdF binder (51 kPa). However, it was slightly worse than for CMC. On the other hand, taking into account societal approach there is doubt if such binder – food component – should be seriously considered as electrode component.

In conclusion, CMC is definitely the best binding substance for capacitor electrodes, especially for organic medium. It shows the best adhesion to the current collector of 2227 kPa. What is more, CMC plays the role of binder perfectly also for electrodes in Li-ion batteries. Solid electrolyte interphase is beneficially compact. It is noteworthy that electrodes with CMC do not lose porosity, which is the case for electrodes with PVdF.

All reported binders reflect the rather bio-oriented way of thinking. Possible elimination of fluoropolymers from electrochemical capacitors is a significant step toward the sustainability of power sources. Though, none of the mentioned biopolymers is actually able to replace PVdF and PTFE at the industrial scale in the near future. Extremely high stability requirements and perspective application as wearable and flexible devices limit the scope of binders to the feature-designed, synthetic ones.

Nowadays new approach using binder-free electrodes arises; sandwich-like cells with gel electrolytes have been proposed [132]. CNT-based composites [133] could be used without polymer binder that improves power performance of the device and sustainable character.

Electrolytes

Aqueous redox active electrolytes

It is worth mentioning that electrochemical performance of aqueous electrolytes has been boosted via adding redox active species. This kind of charge storage mechanism, introduced to electrochemical capacitors in late 2000s aimed at the specific

energy enhancement by fast and reversible redox processes coming from the electrolyte solution. The most common additives studied in water-based electrochemical capacitors are iodides [134] or hydroquinones [135]. Surprisingly, the long-term performance is not suppressed, especially for I₂/I⁻. However, the parameters of aging tests cannot be neglected. Calculation method could lead to overestimated stability of redox active electrolytes [136]. The electrochemical performance of the system is characterized by electrostatic attractions and faradaic processes. Thus, galvanostatic profiles are not characterized anymore by constant voltage slope during charging/discharging. This is why integration of curves should be done in order to calculate either capacitance/capacity or energetic efficiency. Nonetheless, high redox activity of iodides mainly enhances the performance of positive electrode with ongoing reactions:

In symmetric electrochemical capacitor iodides have been tested as additive to the aqueous sulfate-based electrolytes, i.e., MnSO₄ [137], Na₂SO₄ [138] or H₂SO₄ [139] or nitrate-based, i.e., Mg(NO₃)₂ [140]. In all cases, an increase in current density has been recorded which improves energy output of the device.

Figure 11 represents exemplary cyclic voltammograms recorded for the symmetric electrochemical capacitor without and with KI additive. The high current increase could be observed for the positive electrode in the form of reversible redox peak. What is more, iodides' presence does not influence the maximum electrochemical voltage window, reported as 1.5 V for MnSO₄ + KI [137].

As it could be observed in cyclability tests performed in studies with 0.06 M KI in 1 M H₂SO₄ [139], selected regime of 4 A/g is too harsh to allow occurring reactions with iodide activity. This is why special attention should be put on appropriate evaluation of redox active electrolyte performance. Nitrate-based electrolyte [140] with the addition of potassium iodide allows obtaining the voltage of 1.8 V which is even higher than for high-concentrated nitrate solution itself (>5 M).

Quinone-based redox active electrolytes are assumed to give similar enhancement of electrochemical performance as electrode materials modified with quinone/hydroquinone functional groups. Addition of redox active species to the electrolyte is much simpler and cheaper in comparison to sophisticated carbon surface modification [141]. It has been assumed that hydroquinones are incorporated into carbon structure, which results in improved capacitance. However, type and physicochemical characteristics of utilized electrode play a crucial role in quinone/hydroquinone (Q/HQ) contribution to overall performance [142]. What is important in all redox active electrolytes – despite the fact that the most likely enhanced performance is achieved only on one electrode, the electrochemical performance of the symmetric cell is also improved nevertheless not in the same extent. The activity of Q/HQ additive has also been proven with electrically conducting polymers (ECs) [143–145]. It is interesting that system works out during cycling (1st vs. 1000th cycle) what

FIGURE 11

CVs (scan rate = 1 mV s⁻¹) of the individual electrodes for capacitors charged up to 1.5 V: (a) in 2 mol L⁻¹ MnSO₄; (b) in 2 mol L⁻¹ MnSO₄ + 0.5 mol L⁻¹ KI. The dashed vertical lines in the figures represent the thermodynamic hydrogen ($E_H = -0.295$ V vs. NHE) and oxygen evolution ($E_{O_2} = 0.935$ V vs. NHE) potentials at pH = 5 [137].

proves progressive redox reactions. Different combinations have been proposed for quinone-based systems, gel electrolytes with redox additives are the most interesting from the point of view of advanced technology [146–148].

Exploitation of other redox active species certainly requires additional comment. Nowadays, researchers put a lot of effort to find effective, cheap, and reversible redox additives. Very modern approach uses ferricyanide/ferrocyanide redox couple in order to diminish water decomposition reaction [149].

However, the system has not been studied in three-electrode set-up, hence, the reason for such high-voltage of Na₂SO₄-based supercapacitor cannot be clearly defined. It is assumed that redox additive increases the solvation energy, therefore, in high-voltage regime the solvation shell is broken first and water splitting reaction occurs after. Moreover, similar research has been done with additional improvement of construction of the system in order to minimize drawback of this ferricyanide/ferrocyanide redox couple [150]. This system suffered from a large self-discharge phenomena. To some extent, high activity of redox active species might be – on one side – advantageous, as far as high reaction rate is necessary, but on the other hand, shuttling effect might significantly boost the self-discharge phenomenon and energy loss in the system. Immobilization of the redox moieties at respective electrode compartments appears to be a reasonable strategy. Using very expensive, ion-selective membrane instead of typical cellulose separator might diminish the self-discharge rate, but for practical application this solution might be problematic. Still very low efficiency for charging/discharging process is recorded what leads to major critics for that kind of electrolyte.

To summarize, redox active species have been successfully implemented in aqueous electrolytes, which decrease the cost of the final system with enhanced performance. Reported stability of iodides is much higher than quinones, bromides [151], thiocyanates [152], or ferricyanide, which places them on the top in the group of all redox active compounds.

The scientific discussion about the nature of electrochemical capacitors exploiting redox activity from the electrolytic solution

and the classification of such systems as asymmetric or hybrid is recently open. Authors postulate that the ‘label’ has no meaning as far as the comprehensive analysis of the system performance is not done. Detailed instruction for reporting the metrics has been provided by G.Z. Chen with co-workers [153] and in our opinion must be strictly followed in reliable reports.

Solid-state electrolytes

Advanced electrochemical capacitors technologies for miniaturized and smart applications require reliable, safe, bend-resistive solutions. The liquid character of commonly used electrolytes does not follow these criteria as unusual conditions may lead to overpressure inside the device or even to the explosion. Solid-state electrolytes have been proposed to overcome this risk. A series of aqueous-based polymer electrolytes that are proton-conducting, hydroxide ion-conducting or neutral salt ion-conducting have been developed [100]. Polyacrylamide with ionic species, e.g., silicotungstic acid, tetraethylammonium hydroxide, or LiCl were blended into polymer electrolyte systems. They provide a safe alternative to the liquid electrolytes and show promising performance when stretched and flexed (Figure 12). The fabrication procedure usually includes an external preparation of the ionogel (with varying water and salt content) and is followed by placement of the membrane in the final cell. The main advantage of the ionogels is the fact, that the size or shape of the membrane is practically unlimited and might be easily rescaled (Figure 12A–C), depending on the requested cell design. On the other hand, dry cells still suffer from a rather moderate conductivity and capacitance values, since the viscous or solid electrolyte cannot perfectly penetrate the electrode material in order to preserve good conductivity and charge propagation. In this aspect, a rational design (electrode thickness) or in-situ synthesis/gelation would be a perfect solution. However, in-situ gelation might not allow the membrane thickness to be fully controlled.

Among many other polymers such as poly(vinyl alcohol) [154], poly(ethylene oxide) [155] used to prepare solid-state electrolytes, biopolymers have been established as a sustainable and versatile choice essentially for aqueous [156] and IL-based solid ionic conductors. As mentioned in the previous section concerning

FIGURE 12

Scheme of different configurations of polymer electrolyte-based electrochemical capacitors; flexible sandwich configuration (left); interdigitated finger cell (middle); coaxial fiber (right) [132].

the binders, chitosan (CS) may be used as a host for a neutral aqueous electrolyte [97].

The ability of CS to form gel-like electrolytes have been proved a few more times, when applied in systems operating in chitosan/LiClO₄/ethylene carbonate/propylene carbonate [157], plasticized chitosan-starch blend doped with LiClO₄ [158], chitosan/ionic liquids [159] or photopolymerized chitosan/hydroxyethyl methacrylate/IL [160]. Interesting properties of chitosan-based gel electrolyte (aqueous and IL media) have been practically used by Ishikawa et al. [161]. Such examples are shown in Figure 13.

Properties of two most common biopolymers, cellulose, and chitin have been coupled to prepare the acidic chitin-cellulose hybrid gel for electrochemical capacitors [162,163]. These combinations allow obtaining the transparent devices. Hence, their main application is foreseen in personal electronics. It has been studied in a few configurations using H₂SO₄/ionic liquids and shown relatively good performance within the reasonable range of current loadings and temperatures. Cellulose on its own, in the form of nanoparticles, has been used as a host for imidazolium-based IL [13]. Resulting solid-state electrolyte has been studied in transparent and flexible ITO-made electrochemical capacitor. An ITO plate has also been used to assemble electrochemical capacitor with biodegradable gel electrolyte based on agarose and NaCl [164]. A quasi-solid-state electrolyte has shown comparable performance to a liquid equivalent.

Electrochemical studies have been comprehensively supported by bending tests with no failure during both, compressive and tensile bending. This is quite a reasonable study since several works reporting on the flexible devices neglect the influence of external deformation on the electrochemical performance.

Another biodegradable and abundant material, corn-derived starch (consisting of amylose and amylopectin) has been checked as a gelating agent for polymer electrolyte and doped with lithium acetate [165]. Its performance is significantly limited by slow diffusion of ions during charging/discharging and degrades along with some cycles.

Carboxymethylcellulose is often used as a gelating agent of electrolyte in various electrochemical systems. It has also been used for the preparation of flexible all-solid-state thin films with MnO₂ as electrode materials of symmetric capacitors [166]. Na₂SO₄/CMC gel served as an electrolyte, and flexible stainless steel substrate was a current collector where manganese oxide was directly deposited from KMnO₄ solution reduced by oxalic or citric acid. Very high values of capacitance were reached especially when citric acid was used. However, a mass of active material was only ca. 0.2 mg/cm². Areal capacitance was wrongly calculated (it is one order smaller, i.e., ca 150 mF/cm² but not 1500 mF/cm²). Additionally, it is difficult to estimate real stability of such gel electrolyte if cycling was performed only for 2000 cycles. Briefly, solid-state electrolytes offer a lot of opportunities when considering possible future applications of

FIGURE 13

Chitosan-IL (EMImBF₄) gel electrolyte film (left); mixture of activated carbon powder with chitosan aqueous solution with 3-wt.% acetic acid (middle) and poly(ethylene oxide) aqueous solution (right) [161].

FIGURE 14

Scheme of cell construction and material synthesis process for individual components in "all-kelp solid-state electrochemical capacitor" [167].

electrochemical capacitors with one major drawback – poor behavior at high current loadings due to slow ion diffusion in the polymeric host. They still have not been introduced to the industry. Thus, it is difficult to predict if bio-inspired solid-state electrolytes will play a significant role or become just a green alternative to PVA-based electrolytes. Nevertheless, starch has been already found by batteries manufacturers as a promising additive. Hence, one cannot definitely exclude bio-derived from the future application.

It is noteworthy that even if this type of electrolyte is not adapted for heavy regimes, it will limit self-discharge and leakage current of the capacitor. Therefore, it seems to be indispensable for electronic systems where liquid electrolyte should be excluded.

Worth mentioning is the work done by Xin Guo et al. who have demonstrated bio-inspired solid-state supercapacitor built entirely of a single precursor [167]. This kind of device is suitable for wearable electronics. The key components (electrolyte, electrode, separator and binder) come from abundant food resource from ocean, i.e., kelp. As graphically shown in Figure 14, Na-based hydrogel electrolyte, membrane separator, and binder are extracted from kelp. Sodium alginate is a natural polysaccharide. Activated carbon material was directly made from natural dry kelp. It was firstly washed with deionized water, then dried at 70 °C and carbonized. The carbonization process was carried out into a tube furnace at 600 °C in Ar atmosphere. Afterward, obtained product was activated via impregnation of the carbonized material in KOH (mass ratio of carbon:KOH equals to 1:4). The following steps include slurry drying and thermal treatment at 750 °C in Ar. At the end, samples were washed with 10 wt.% of HCl solution, water and finally dried. Assembled solid-state capacitor was tested showing satisfactory rate capability (156 F/g at 20 A/g) and good cycling stability.

Other electrochemical capacitor's components

Accordingly to the sustainability issues touched in this review, influence of other components, such as: separators, packaging and current collectors, cannot be neglected. The bio-derived materials cannot be suppressed by utilization of non-accepted components. Separators should be ecologically friendly or at least with negligible impact on the environment. In this regard, glass fibers or cellulose papers appear to be the best choice. In sustainable electrochemical capacitor, expensive (sophisticated, semi-permeable membranes) or environmental unfriendly materials (PP) should be definitely avoided.

Device packaging needs to be adjusted to the future application and designed for specific demand (gravimetric and volumetric energy/power, cyclability, etc.). For portable electronics, capacitors should be light and as small as possible, therefore, polymer packaging is recommended. For energy storage in vehicles, such as trams or trains, the volume or mass do not play a crucial role. In this particular case, packaging should be extremely resistant to the external factors, such as temperature, humidity, vibrations or weather conditions.

To obtain good rate capability of the material, the adhesion between current collector and electrode material should be considered. Therefore, rheological parameters of the slurry should be carefully investigated and its resistivity to shrinking, cracking, breaking or/and bending need to be studied. Material of current collector should match the electrolyte type. Apparently, the stainless steel (with various additives) perfectly fulfills the requirements for neutral, aqueous solutions. In order to improve long-term performance and to ensure the protection against corrosion, formation of additional carbon coating might be an interesting solution. However, the thickness and type of such a layer must be individually checked. In organic-based

systems, the current collectors most often used are made of aluminum and copper. Obviously, the selection depends on the type of the electrode used in the system (symmetric or hybrid device).

Briefly, the sustainability of all components is a crucial parameter which needs to be considered in addition to bio-derived and eco-friendly materials. 'Sustainable' label should be placed on the products built entirely of the components meeting all the criteria.

Concluding remarks

Development of novel power sources and optimization of those already existing is the fundamental mission to provide clean energy in case of critical depletion of natural resources. Materials of natural origin are more and more introduced to the field of electrochemical capacitors and display comparable performance to the synthetic ones. Having in mind a widespread abundance, low cost, biodegradability, biopolymers and biomass-derived materials are sustainable alternatives for established commercial products. Their future application will highly depend on technology that ECs are used for. They can be useful for not demanding, already established solutions. However, novel challenging concepts of electrochemical capacitors surely require more advanced and sustainable biomaterials to be used.

Even if a lot of research has been performed on a food product (sugar-based, bovine milk, protein, etc.), such precursor will never be considered in practice.

In conclusion, only by-products from food industry should be considered as carbon precursor (e.g., coffee grounds, various seeds, shells, etc.), and their availability should also be taken into consideration. For example, using the seeds from olives seems to be obvious in Spain where the olive trees grow in large [168,169]. In this case, they can fulfill some local (but not global) demand as a carbon precursor [170]. To some extent, such a finding reflects the flexibility in using 'sustainable' term but does not allow to draw a general conclusion without well-backgrounded explanation.

For the global request, coconut shells will be still indispensable as the most abundant. The next widespread source of natural resources could be the seaweeds. As it was mentioned before, seaweeds contain a broad spectrum of alkali metals which play a role of self-activator during carbonization process that gives economically affordable carbon material. However, their use as carbon precursor might be regulated by law and environment protection of the country.

Biopolymers such as cellulose, chitosan, or starch were successfully introduced to the electrochemical capacitors field as binders and electrolyte modifiers. However, there is still a lot of research necessary to face the limitations demonstrated by these systems (low conductivity, moderate response time, cyclability).

Finally, in our opinion, the term 'sustainable' is quite often overused, mainly in very general statements, since some economic and geographic conditions may not apply to everything. This word should not be placed as a decoration of the paper only since the meaning is well-defined: "conserving an ecological balance by avoiding depletion of natural resources". Not everything must be absolutely 'green' or 'eco-friendly', but our devel-

opment strategy must be oriented toward balanced and well-understood environment protection.

The perspectives emerging from bio-derived carbons focus on the synthesis method and the activation process. Researchers should consider precursors which include activator and are locally abundant. Nowadays, many trends could be observed in utilization and re-usage of wastes from different industries; this seems to be very promising approach. In order to create sustainable electrode materials, not only its textural, structural, and chemical properties should be considered but also its rheological parameters. Thus, both physicochemical characteristics and studies of adhesion to the current collector should be carried out. Moreover, from all hydrothermal-based methods, the emphasis should be focused on those which are possible to be scaled-up. For instance, microwave-assisted hydrothermal synthesis of AC greatly shortens the time of production process and reduces an overall cost of the material. Verifying the newest publication record related to the 'sustainability' subject, authors optimistically look at development of bio-derived carbons, however, misleading results cannot be accepted. This is why evaluating criteria should be appropriately selected both for the type of material and its further application.

In our opinion, further development of sustainable and bio-sourced materials should be oriented toward enhancement of their long-term performance. Furthermore, identifying the degradation mechanisms, supported by more and more advanced *operando* techniques, should definitely help in understanding the mysteries of electrode/electrolyte interface. We do not pretend to discard the development of novel, 'exotic' forms of the (carbon) materials; in our opinion, as far as they contribute to broadening the horizons and allow the knowledge to be gained, the research is justified. This is rather to say, that the results should be reported in accordance with best scientific practices, even if the results are not 'outstanding'. "What is right is not always popular and what is popular is not always right" (A. Einstein).

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